

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 1.6: Recommendations focusing on Social Sciences and Humanities expertise

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This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordination and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

This report has been developed in collaboration between the author(s)/editor and the contributors listed below.

Disclaimer

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1 INTRODUCTION

The "Study on CCS Transport, Storage, and the Just Transition" was commissioned by the Zero Emissions Platform in alignment with Horizon Europe rules, which emphasises the integration of social sciences and humanities in projects. As part of these requirements, the study aimed to create a stronger link between CCS initiatives and social sciences to address the Just Transition to a net-zero economy. Recognising the need for specialised expertise, the ZEP secretariat found it necessary to submit a request for proposal to commission an external study, conducted by Opergy Group. It offers a comprehensive analysis of the employment and skills requirements for the CCS supply chain across ten European countries, highlighting the transition potential for the workforce from fossil fuels to CCS.

The deliverable was discussed within the Consortium Agreement, with the ZEP Secretary-General seeking advice from grant holders. The secretariat drafted and published a request for proposal (RfP) on the ZEP website and social media channels, setting a submission deadline of 2 February 2024. The RfP invited proposals from researchers affiliated with think-tanks, academic institutes, or relevant organisations, particularly those with social sciences credentials. The secretariat received six applications and Opergy Group's proposal was identified as the most promising, leading to further discussions and a revised proposal that incorporated feedback from the ZEP Advisory Council Executive Committee and Consortium Agreement holders. The study aimed to provide actionable recommendations for policymakers and project developers to ensure CCS projects facilitate a just transition.

The Carbon Capture and Storage Association ASBL (CCSA ASBL) views the study as a valuable and insightful contribution to understanding the employment dynamics and skills requirements associated with CCS infrastructure. The study highlights that a significant surge in skilled labour demand will occur towards the end of the 2020s, particularly in countries like Belgium, the Netherlands, Norway, and the UK. This surge aligns with the construction phase of CCS projects, followed by a notable decline once the infrastructure is established.

The study includes a detailed breakdown of job roles, such as asset operations, civil construction, drilling/wells, and mechanical and technical skills, emphasising that many of these skills are already present within the existing oil and gas workforce. This indicates a relatively smooth transition for workers moving from fossil fuel sectors to CCS roles. However, it is important to note the need for strategic workforce planning to manage the fluctuating labour demand effectively, ensuring sustained employment opportunities.

Overall, the CCSA ASBL believes the study provides essential insights for policymakers and project developers. By highlighting the potential for a just transition and the socioeconomic impacts of CCS deployment, the study supports the development of informed strategies to achieve a sustainable, low-carbon economy. The findings underscore the need for ongoing support and reskilling initiatives to maintain a skilled workforce capable of driving the CCS sector forward. Due to the limitations mentioned, the study provides an indicative, rather than an exhaustive, view of the employment that CCS deployment can create in various countries.

The study is attached to this deliverable report as a separate document.

Study on Carbon Capture, Storage and the Just Transition

A Study for the Zero Emissions Platform

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Study on Carbon Capture, Storage and the Just Transition

1	INTRODUCTION.....	3
1.1	AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY.....	3
1.2	PROJECT DELIVERY.....	3
1.3	CITATIONS OF SIMILAR WORK.....	4
2	METHODOLOGY	6
2.1	CORE PROCESS.....	6
2.2	DETAILED PROCESS.....	6
2.3	MANUFACTURING.....	8
2.4	DEMAND.....	8
2.5	TERMINOLOGY.....	8
3	RESULTS.....	10
3.1	RESULTS - OVERALL	10
3.2	RESULTS - BELGIUM.....	10
3.3	RESULTS - CROATIA	12
3.4	RESULTS - DENMARK.....	14
3.5	RESULTS - FRANCE.....	16
3.6	RESULTS - GERMANY.....	18
3.7	RESULTS - GREECE	21
3.8	RESULTS - ITALY	22
3.9	RESULTS - NETHERLANDS.....	24
3.10	RESULTS - NORWAY	26
3.11	RESULTS - UK.....	28
	APPENDIX A: ASSUMPTIONS	35
	APPENDIX B: OPERGY COMMON PEOPLE & SKILLS TAXONOMY	37
	APPENDIX C: LIST OF SOURCES AND CONTRIBUTORS.....	35

1 Introduction

1.1 Aims and Objectives of the Study

Opergy Group is very pleased to provide this report and its findings. This study has been an invaluable exercise, drawing from Opergy's longstanding knowledge and expertise in CCS and the energy sector as a whole to provide useful intelligence around the present state of much of Europe's CCS employment base. The report also provides an indication on the ability of several key European Oil & Gas markets to facilitate a workforce transition from fossil fuels to CCS.

The Zero Emissions Platform tasked and worked with Opergy to reach out to several key contacts, working on CCS projects in ten different European countries. Using Opergy's Regional Employment Calculators, we were able to input the findings of our stakeholder engagement to provide robust, country specific employment estimates. This report shares these estimates, providing an understanding of their implications.

The ten countries selected for analysis were as follows:

- Belgium
- Croatia
- Denmark
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Italy
- Netherlands
- Norway
- United Kingdom

These projects are upscaled based on the known pipeline of current active projects. Due to a combination of factors, namely the scope of the project and the accessibility of complete project pipeline data, some projects have, inevitably been omitted. Therefore, whilst the employment estimates associated with the chosen projects/companies are based on actual estimates, gained through industry engagement (or through modelling), national figures are scaled up. A full list of assumptions, taking into account unique national considerations and economies of scale are provided in Appendix A.

Due to the limitations mentioned, the study provides an indicative, rather than an exhaustive, view of the employment that CCS deployment can create in various countries.

1.2 Project Delivery

In February 2024, Opergy Group was appointed via a competitive tender process to undertake this study. In our bid, we proposed to structure the study around two key questions:

- What is the employment and skills requirement for CCS transport and storage projects currently planned in the ten CCS leading European Nations? (in the interests of wider European representation, this was expanded to include ten nations).
- What is the potential for cross-sector transferability between oil and gas sectors and CCS?

What Opergy offered, was an expertise led solution, building on our significant and growing portfolio of projects undertaken relating to CCS, energy sector employment and the workforce transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy. The original scope was to estimate employment in the power generation sector. This however, shifted to focus solely on the Transport & Storage component of the value chain. Having completed extensive work estimated employment for CCS, focusing on the Transport and Storage stages of the project, Opergy were in a very strong position to deliver this contract to as high a level as possible.

A complete breakdown of the methodology employed can be found in the methodology section.

Broadly though, this project began with a European CCS market study. Building on this, ten projects and companies were selected. By engaging with relevant contacts at these companies, working on the chosen projects, we were able to gain the necessary understanding of the projects' estimated employment requirements.

Based on additional research conducted into all the major CCS projects across the chosen European countries, the intelligence gained through stakeholder engagement could be upscaled. Using this pipeline of projects, these estimates could be forecast. This was achieved using the Opergy Group Regional Employment Estimate Calculators, also able to provide additional detail and context behind the nature of the CCS workforce.

Quality Assurance was conducted by cross-referencing our findings with our previous CCS employment estimate work and by discussing in detail the overarching assumptions that underpinned this report.

1.3 Citations of Similar Work

There are a number of other studies that align with and support the work we have conducted as part of this project. A full list of data sources can be found in Appendix C, however, the below lists the reports that best align with the project.

Energy Skills Intelligence Hub (ESIH), updated Feb 2024 – Opito/Opergy

Power Sector Regional Employment Estimates, Dec 2023 – DESNZ/Opergy

CCSA Workforce & Skills Position Paper, July 2023 – CCSA

CCS Supply Chain Plan, March 2024 - UKRI

2 Methodology

In order to scale up employment to reflect the national workforces of each chosen country, the Opergy Regional Power Sector Calculator for CCUS was used. Before adapting them for use for each country, several components were stripped out. Firstly, the functionality to provide intranational regional data was stripped out. As much of the employment will take place offshore, especially at storage sites, intranational regional data is much less relevant. Also, since the study only aims to provide employment intelligence for transport and storage, all data around the capture process itself has also been stripped out. Otherwise, additional functionality and data particular to the UK was removed and has been adapted to accommodate for any non-particular or country specific inputs and variables.

The following sections detail the core components of how the calculators were built, the input assumptions and the way in which the employment estimates were generated. There is the core process, outlining the major working principles factored into the calculator.

2.1 Core Process

At a high level the following approach was used:

1. For the modelling approach, we engaged a team of experts to review project sizes, splitting these, where appropriate, into different categories as there can be significant differences from scale.
2. Using single or multiple phase durations the number of jobs in each phase for each year that phase is active for were assigned. This gives us the phase employment splits. Four asset phases have been identified: Development, Manufacturing (excluded from study), Construction and Operations & Maintenance. Corporate Service roles, expected to exist throughout the project lifecycle, have also been assumed.
3. The skills required at each of these phases are then categorised according to the Opergy Common People & Skills Taxonomy (see Appendix B). By using a common nomenclature, estimating the job families and roles required to perform key tasks in CCS Transport & Storage becomes simpler and much more consistent.
4. The phase employment splits are aligned to the year of first power for each project in the pipeline data options. These options are:
 - a. The known pipeline of projects which Opergy has gained from verifiable sources.
 - b. A set of projected projects which Opergy has projected from industry knowledge and other sources.
5. A number of other variables are assigned to each technology; productivity improvements and technology improvements.

2.2 Detailed Process

All the input employment data for CCS was gained through industry engagement and through research. As data and information was collected, work was needed to categorise and

homogenise it, fitting it into a consistent nomenclature for project phasing (i.e. does the job take place during the Development, Construction, Operations & Maintenance phase or is it a corporate role that takes place throughout the lifespan of the project?)

Based on prior engagement and expertise, the skills required to deliver CCS Transport & Storage projects are aligned to the Opergy People & Skills Common Taxonomy. Comprised of 19 individual job families, themselves broken down into over 80 job family sub groups, the taxonomy is used to provide a robust estimate of the types of jobs that will likely be required to meet the demands of each country's project pipeline. To provide further information around some of the typical job titles linked to each job family sub group, an additional column in Appendix B has been added.

Once the year-by-year employment splits had been apportioned for each project phase, they were then projected onto the project pipeline, in real time. This pivoted around the operational date of the transport and storage facilities/sites. Once the data was aggregated and in-effect calendarised, industrial 'improvement factors' were applied. Based on research conducted by various organisations, including the Offshore Renewable Energy Catapult (OREC) and other experienced industry experts, the improvement factors are based on an assumption that natural changes in industrial processes will result in small reductions in the amount of work/effort required to perform the same task, year-on-year. Their use ultimately seeks to paint a more accurate picture of the likely changes in employment trends, producing more reliable employment estimates. They are categorised in two ways:

Industry productivity – these are the gains made as industry gets better at performing the same tasks, whether it be through designing, building, re-purposing or operating the transport and storage infrastructure. In other words, as workers become more familiar with the key repeated process involved in transport and storage, they are likely to gradually become more efficient in performing these tasks over time.

Technology improvements – these are the gains made as technology improves. As innovation and R&D improve, as could be the case in quicker and more efficient methods of CO₂ storage, technology can gradually replace tasks typically performed, or tasks that require an element, of manual labour.

Based on the work conducted as described earlier, the expected annual reductions are estimated to be:

1. 1.25% per annum (on a compound basis) as a reduction factor for productivity; and
2. 2.5% per annum (on a compound basis) as a reduction factor for technology improvements.

The combined year-on-year effect on the future people and skill of productivity & efficiency increases					
2030	2031	2032	2033	2034	2035
100.00%	98.75%	97.50%	96.25%	95.00%	93.75%

The combined year-on-year effect on the future people and skill of industry technology improvements					
2030	2031	2032	2033	2034	2035
100.00%	97.50%	95.00%	92.50%	90.00%	87.50%

Above: the compound effect of Productivity & Efficiency and Industry Technology Improvements on the Fixed Offshore Wind industry workforce

The sector's relative industrial maturity or immaturity affects the point at which the reductions are made. Since CCS is a relatively immature industry, it is unlikely that any major gains from improved productivity and efficiency or technology advancement will be seen until 2030, once the sector reaches a significant industrial scale. However, this also means the annual impact of these factors will be more pronounced at the beginning. As CCS is a relatively immature industry, the rate at which newer processes are learned and the rate at which technological solutions proliferate is faster than for more mature industries. For example, reductions in productivity & efficiency and technology for mature, established industries like Oil & Gas and onshore wind are likely to be minimal. Likewise, as the industry matures, these reductions will increase. Therefore, it is estimated that the combined reductions from these efficiencies will not fall below 75% of what it was at the beginning.

Linked to this, is the country's CCS industry itself. In countries like Norway and the UK, where a higher number of projects are expected to be operational around 2030, these efficiency reductions can be expected as early as 2031. Countries with fewer projects planned for the same period are more likely to face a delay in the onset of these reductions. This has therefore been a key consideration for estimating future employment.

2.3 Manufacturing

There is a strong and growing supply chain for manufacturing CO₂ Transport & Storage across Europe and in the rest of the world. CCS provides significant opportunities for the manufacturing labour force to further expand. At this stage though, measuring manufacturing is a significant challenge and estimates around employment at a national level are not likely to be accurate. This is due to several reasons. A major reason is that it requires a strong understanding of local content. Percentages of manufacturing content, let alone for components and equipment that CCS rely on, are difficult to find and estimate. Though it would be possible to estimate these percentages based on the known role manufacturing plays for each economy (e.g. France and Italy have higher local content percentages than the UK, but comparably smaller than Germany's) this is unlikely to provide a robust estimate for which employment can be accurately estimated. With a high volume of manufacturing being completed outside of Europe, in countries like the United States, China, South Korea, Indonesia, Australia and others), it would be very challenging to provide a reliable estimate on the number of manufacturing jobs created in each country, and the effect this has on European markets.

2.4 Demand

The insights provided from Opergy's engagement with several key European CCS industry contacts has been highly valuable to this study. Without this level of engagement, reaching an understanding of each country's national industrial context would have been far more challenging. Nevertheless, where engagement has not been possible/has not been achieved, modelling has been used. For furthermore details on how employment modelling is achieved, see the 2.1 Core Process section. However, since the modelling is based on estimated employment requirements for CCS Transport and Storage, the resulting estimates are 'demand-based.' In other words, these estimates are based on anticipated needs for the development of a

CCS Transport & Storage project from initial development up until (not including) decommissioning.

Demand is also central to understanding how projects are scheduled. The project pipeline, developed through industry engagement and extensive desk-based research, produces a reliable estimate of the statuses of each project and the planned dates at which each project enters commercial operations. However, it cannot account for exogenous factors that may result in potential delays or possible cancellations. International political events (i.e. a pandemic or conflict), macroeconomic crises (i.e. inflation and cost of living challenges) and even changes in national governments (i.e. different approaches to energy security following national elections) can have fundamental impacts on the progress or even continued development of projects. The list of factors is not exhaustive; delays may be caused for various other reasons. However, because the arrival of these factors is at best very challenging to predict, the official milestone dates found through research or provided through industry engagement have been assumed as likely. As a result, estimates are based on the employment demands as anticipated year-by-year, according to these dates.

2.5 Terminology

A key challenge to estimating employment, whether in CCS, Oil & Gas or other industrial sectors, is fitting key terms and concepts into a consistent nomenclature. It is the norm that different organisations and industries will use different names to describe the same role. It is for this reason that Opergy have developed the 'Common People & Skills Taxonomy' (see Appendix B). For similar reasons, much of the intelligence and data acquired through prior industry engagement recognises Transport and Storage differently, especially as this typically includes onshore and offshore infrastructure. For the purposes of this report, transport will refer to logistical infrastructure (e.g. ships, rail) and onshore pipeline networks. Storage will refer to the actual offshore infrastructure, including the storage site/platform, the subsea wells and the offshore pipeline. Another reason for drawing this distinction is that the job levels linked to the offshore infrastructure differ depending on whether CO₂ is being stored in saline aquifers or depleted oil or gas reservoirs. Because of this, 'storage' jobs include the offshore pipeline as well.

3 Results

Below is a breakdown of the employment estimates, aggregating data nationally and across all chosen countries. At a national level, the breakdown includes the major types of industry, the method of transportation used for each project (whether the project uses pipeline, logistics or a combination of the two), the method of storage (whether the storage site is a brownfield site, a greenfield site or multiple sites, combining both, is used), expected CO₂ captured, transported and stored, year of first operations and both total jobs. In the vast majority of cases, logistics refers to shipping, and standard vessels dimensions and vessel quantities have been assumed (see Appendix A). However, there are rail and road-based solutions increasing being pursued as well. At an overall level, the main emitter industries are listed, as well as national CO₂ captured, transported and stored and national total jobs. To provide an indication of typical employment for a Transport & Storage project, the mean or 'average jobs' have been calculated and included.

3.1 Results Summary

The following table summarises the headline results for all geographies considered.

Country	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Peak Year	Total Jobs (Peak Year)	Total Jobs (2030)	Total Jobs (2040)
Belgium	27.5 – 54.0	2029	4810	1850	250
Croatia	1.0	2025	1060	200	170
Denmark	11.5 – 38.0	2029	560	380	190
France	2.5	2027	460	170	110
Germany	4.0	2027	260	1760	170
Greece	3.5 – 4.0	2024	150	80	60
Italy	10.0 – 40.0	2024	200	80	60
Netherlands	12.5	2025	1880	1830	220
Norway	65.5	2027	1880	580	440
UK	75.0	2036	2400	1750	940
Total	213 – 296.5	N/A	13660	8680	2610

3.2 Results - Belgium

The results for Belgium are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
Antwerp@C	-Chemicals	Both	N/A - No decision taken yet	Phase One: 2.5 Phase Two: 10	Phase One: 2026 Phase 2: 2030
North Sea Pipeline Zeebrugge	-Cement -Chemicals -Refineries -Steel -Waste incinerators	N/A	Brownfield	20 - 40	2030

Ghent Carbon Hub	-Oil & Gas	Both	Brownfield	4	2028
H2BE Project	-Blue Hydrogen	Logistics	N/A – likely to be linked to other infrastructure	N/A	2028

Despite the relative uncertainty around Belgium's CCS Transport and Storage pipeline – largely owing to the unconfirmed status of Antwerp@C project and the expected infrastructural integration of the H2BE project – the Belgian transport & storage labour market is forecast to perform strongly. With total employment expected to range between 500 and 1,200 in the next two years, it is then expected to accelerate through to 2030, reaching a peak of over 4800 jobs by the end of the decade. By far the largest driver of this peak is the expected construction and assembly of Equinor's and Fluxy's major cross-border CO₂ transport pipeline. The subsea pipeline, extending over 1,000km across the North Sea, will play a significant role in transporting much of the CO₂ produced in North-West Europe's industrial markets. The delivery of this pipeline could require hundreds of skilled, semi-skilled and manual operatives, providing opportunities for engineers, civil construction operatives, offshore technicians, quality control managers as well as onshore and offshore vehicle drivers and equipment handlers. Post-peak, this project will likely require significant Operations & Maintenance expertise. Requiring as many as 150 O&M jobs per year – as much as 60% of all of Belgium's projected CCS O&M employment post-2032 – there are many opportunities for skilled asset operators and mechanics. Specific roles may include service/maintenance technicians, mechanical technicians, statutory inspectors and control room operators. However, as this project is cross-border, projecting employment and skills needs at national level offers different challenges. Since, as previously explained, estimates are largely demand-based, they reflect the particular requirements needed to perform the activities necessary for the project's overall delivery. As a result, the projections do not factor in the likely contribution made by Norwegian developers at the other end of the

pipeline. As the project progresses, this may become clearer, making it easier to estimate the proportion of employment generated in Norway.

When factoring in other Belgian projects, namely Antwerp@C, Ghent Carbon Hub and the H2BE project, the skills makeup is, as it is likely to be for other countries, more diverse. Given Belgium's proximity to the North Sea, its comparably higher use of logistical solutions for transporting CO₂ is not surprising. Operating and maintaining the vessels will require a range of skilled, semi-skilled and manual jobs, including skippers, harbour masters, deck operatives, seafarers and quayside operatives. Post-peak, as many as 60 O&M personnel per year may be required. The remaining O&M roles will mostly be accounted for by the maintenance staff for onshore pipeline infrastructure and the corporate service and management staff likely tied to the project but they may not all be required on-site.

Since Belgium is not a major producer of Oil or Natural Gas, the opportunities for cross-sector transferability are likely not as significant as is the case with other countries. However, its reliance on imports, particularly from countries like the Netherlands and Norway, has helped position Belgium as a cross-border transport hub for natural gas. By acting as a natural gas flow network between France, Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, the UK and other European markets, it is likely that there is a small workforce of skilled, semi-skilled and manual pipeline maintenance technicians and gas transmission system (there are currently two in Belgium) operators. Also, the current gas conversion project taking place, in which Belgium's existing L-gas network is being reconfigured to support H-gas, will require some of the same management, engineering, assembly and civil construction skills needed for developing much of the onshore pipeline infrastructure. However, with little available data on the size of Belgium's oil and gas sector, estimating the transferability of skills in these industries to CCS transport and storage is not currently possible. Nevertheless, as explained previously, the absence of a mature oil or gas market in Belgium means that the workforce is likely not large enough to fulfil a significant amount of the projected CCS transport and storage workforce.

3.3 Results - Croatia

The results for Croatia are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
GT Geothermal CCS	-Cement	Onshore Pipeline	Greenfield (in Hungary, excluded from study)	0.6	2029
KOdeCO	-Cement	Both	Greenfield & Brownfield	0.35	2028
Petrokemija Kutina	-Ammonia	Onshore Pipeline	Brownfield	0.2	2026

The employment peak in Croatia's CCS transport and storage market is projected to occur next year, exceeding 1000 jobs. With three projects expected to enter commercial operation between 2026 and 2029, the vast majority of jobs projected to be created will be involved in the construction and assembly of the logistical, pipeline (onshore and offshore) and storage site infrastructure in support of them. Despite only being three CCS Transport & Storage projects planned for commercial operations, the unique industrial solutions being pursued for each project suggest a diverse portfolio of trades and skills may be required. The new anticipated onshore pipeline infrastructure developed for the GT Geothermal CCS project, which is expected to transport CO₂ from industrial emitters (mostly cement factories) in Croatia and Hungary would require an adequately sized and trained workforce of highly skilled engineers. Combined with the expected repurposed pipeline linked to the Petrokemija Jutina project, as many as 400 engineers may be required per year of construction. The majority of these will be highly skilled civil and mechanical engineers. This number will rise significantly when factoring in offshore storage requirements, which will include the subsea pipelines needed to connect the capture site(s) to the subsea wells. The use of logistical solutions for transporting CO₂ may also provide opportunities for people with strong maritime skills. If the vessels are new builds, this will likely require small teams of marine engineers, semi-skilled civil construction operatives, skilled marine & port operatives and semi-skilled mechanical operatives (e.g. mechanics). Health & Safety officers will also be required to oversee the handling of the CO₂ carriers. Post-peak, the standard operational activities will be expected, requiring around 200 jobs per year to maintain and monitor the onshore and offshore infrastructure. This will also include corporate service staff who may not all work on site.

What makes the construction labour profile appear different when compared to other countries is the duration, especially for offshore storage infrastructure. From prior industry engagement into archetypal CCS storage projects in the UK, it had been established that the construction phase of the offshore infrastructure takes around five to six years, depending in the particular

storage solution being pursued. However, our recent engagement with stakeholders linked to the KODECO net zero CCS project – a project aiming to capture, transport and permanently store the CO₂ produced by a Koromačno based cement plant – indicated that the construction phase could be as little as two years. However, when comparing the current projections for the volume of CO₂ being captured and stored (0.36 million tonnes per annum for KODECO), it is perhaps not surprising that the construction phase for this project is completed much quicker when compared to projects in other countries. As the other projects in Croatia are aiming to capture, transport and store a similar volume of CO₂ to KODECO, these assumptions were extended to these other projects.

Though it is difficult to estimate and predict the quantitative extent of the employment transferability from Croatia's Oil & Gas workforce to CCS, there is clearly potential. By current estimates, there are between 7000 and 8000 people working in Croatia's Oil & Gas industry, including roughly 1500 in upstream Oil & Gas. With Oil & Gas production declining, CCS has the potential to accommodate for potential workers who leave this industry. With a long heritage in Oil & Gas production, dating back to the early 1950s, many of the key skills mutually required are long-established and well-placed for the transition to newer industries like CCS. Much of the offshore drilling/wells workforce, including drilling supervisors, offshore installation managers, drilling engineers, field engineers and derrickmen have the offshore skills required. Based on estimated drilling/wells employment ratios (see Annex A for assumptions), as many as **200** employees may be needed as peak to satisfy demand in **2025**, equivalent to one-seventh of the country's upstream Oil & Gas workforce. As this equates to a significant amount of the upstream Oil & Gas workforce, it is likely that any skills cross-over will be from part-time workers or newly skilled recruits. However, as Croatia's Oil & Gas production continues to decline and CCS continues to industrially mature, many of the Operations & Maintenance skills/jobs, namely skilled, semi-skilled and manual asset operators and offshore Health and Safety inspectors required by the former may discover opportunities in the latter.

3.4 Results – Denmark

The results for Denmark are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
DUC Bitfrost	Insufficient information	Both	Brownfield	3	2030
Fidelis Norne Hub	-Cement Production -Chemicals -Steel	Both (Unconfirmed)	Greenfield	Phase 1: 10 Phase 2: 30	Phase 1: 2027 Phase 2: 2030
Greensand	-Bioenergy -Cement	Both	Brownfield	Phase 1: 1.5 Phase 2: 8	Phase 1: 2025 Phase 2: 2030

As some key project decisions relating to Denmark's CCS Transport & Storage pipeline await to get made, estimating the employment profile and overall levels is slightly more challenging. The phasing of Operations & Maintenance for the Fidelis Norne Hub and Greensand projects may have an impact on the scheduling for the Construction phase. It is also unconfirmed whether or not the Fidelis Norne Hub will definitely pursue both logistical and onshore pipeline solutions. Both of these factors have the potential to alter both the profile and employment levels linked to each of these projects. A likely result of both is a relative flattening of the two peaks projected to take place in 2024 and 2030. Overall, the construction and assembly of the onshore and offshore infrastructure is likely to peak at over **500** jobs, with a marginally higher peak by the end of the decade. The first of these two peaks is likely to be linked to the Fidelis Norne Hub. This is largely driven by the Greensand and Fidelis Norne Hub projects, which are projected to enter the first phase of their commercial operations by 2027 and 2030 respectively. Like Croatia and the Netherlands, the vast majority of the jobs accounting for this peak will be from the Civil Construction, Drilling/Wells, Technical and Marine & Ports job families. However, as is not the case with these two countries, a much lower proportion of these jobs (less than 10%) are estimated to be linked to onshore pipeline infrastructure or in shipbuilding. Several factors have driven this. The use of older onshore pipeline infrastructure for DUC Bifrost and Fidelis Norne Hub, the absence of any major onshore pipeline network linked to Project Greensand (CO₂ is instead likely to be transported via ships from Belgium) is estimated to flatten the demand for jobs relating to new pipeline construction. The logistical solutions being pursued by all projects will likely generate opportunities for skills based in the Marine & Ports job family. These could include marine engineers, marine superintendents, mooring masters and other additional deck crew. Other relevant roles include painters (around two per vessel) and Health & Safety officers. Once peak construction and assembly has passed, it is expected that operation and general maintenance of the vessels will account for roughly half (between **40** and **50** jobs) of all transport jobs and up to a quarter of all jobs.

The opportunities for a just transition in Denmark are wide. Benefitting from its direct proximity to the North Sea, Denmark is an historically major producer of oil and gas. As oil and gas production continues to steadily decline (producing less than 25% of what it produced twenty years ago, by most recent estimates), the expansion of CCS offers very strong employment opportunities. According to the most recent estimates, there are approximately **26000** direct and indirect Danish jobs in the oil and gas sector. Should CCS mature and expand in Denmark, it has strong potential to accommodate for many of these jobs. A significant proportion of these jobs can be secured from Drilling/Wells activities. Transferable roles from skilled and management backgrounds in Drilling/Wells could include drillers, field engineers, offshore installation manager, maintenance superintendents and drilling supervisors. Transferable skills from semi-skilled and manual backgrounds could include derrickmen, roustabouts and floor hands. It is difficult to estimate the proportion of the workforce that works in upstream oil and gas production. However, based on ratios for countries where this information is available, a very rough estimate would place this figure between **4000** and **5000**. Whilst not robust enough to form the basis of employment forecasting, it strongly suggests that upstream oil and gas employment is within the thousands. Given that the current project pipeline is projected to demand around 200 jobs per annum once operational, it is likely that, with wider industry support, many of the roles could be filled with skilled upstream oil and gas workers. Even if the CCS Transport & Storage pipeline expands, the size of the relevantly skilled workforce is likely to be sufficient in addressing this hypothetical demand. A hypothetical expansion of the CCS Transport & Storage project pipeline could provide further opportunities for professionals with experience in construction and assembling the oil platforms, particularly professionals with civil and mechanical engineering backgrounds.

3.5 Results – France

The results for France are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
Pycasso	-Cement -Glass -Steel -Waste-to-energy -Zinc	Both	Brownfield	2.5	Phase 1: 2030 Phase 2: 2035

The French CCS industry is also relatively immature. Although the French Government announced in June 2023 that a new 'Carbon Contracts for Difference (CCFD) mechanism would be launched, whereby companies submit proposals for low-carbon projects, there is currently only one confirmed project in the pipeline, Pycasso. Construction of the storage site – specifically designed ships and rail-based storage – is expected to produce a slightly prolonged peak of around four hundred or ships before falling as the project enters commercial operation. Most of these roles will be skilled and semi-skilled civil construction operatives. Typical roles will include steelfixers, plant operatives, scaffolders, etc. A notable distinction of the French CCS Transport & Storage employment profile when compared to other countries is the higher employment requirements for transport, rather than for storage. This will likely be driven by the fact that Pycasso has planned multimodal transport solutions, requiring onshore pipeline, ship and rail services. Also, the development of an onshore storage site, thereby removing the substantial employment demands for offshore infrastructure, significantly reduces storage's impact on jobs. As a result, jobs are expected to peak at around **200** in 2028.

Operating and maintaining the four estimated ships, the specialised freight services and the onshore storage site itself will likely support between **70** and **150** jobs from 2030 until 2050. A majority of these jobs will be skilled and semi-skilled asset operators, including control room operators, plant operators, riggers, painters etc. Logistical transport solutions will also play a key part in supporting employment during this phase. To operate the estimated four ships carrying the CO₂, hull inspectors, painting inspectors and machinery inspectors will be required. Though there is less available data around the types of roles needed for operating and maintaining the rail-based CO₂ transport solutions, they are likely to require Health & Safety inspectors, skilled and semi-skilled asset operators and logistical operatives (e.g. train drivers). A head office, where the project's typical corporate activities take place, will also house some off-site jobs. Based on industry engagement, a similar number of jobs will be required for ship-based and rail-based solutions.

Similar to countries like Belgium, France is not a major producer of oil and gas. As a result, almost all of these products are imported. Therefore, it is likely that the potential for cross-sector transferability is more likely to be found in the transport, rather than storage component of CCS. The significant port and pipeline infrastructure used for transporting CO₂ will likely require skills from the Asset Operations, Technical and Marine job families e.g. painters, maintenance technicians, crane operators quayside operatives and a combination of civil, marine and mechanical engineers. Due to the small size of France’s oil and gas industry, recent job estimates are not readily available. However, based on the requirements of its legacy oil and gas transport infrastructure, this is very likely to be in the hundreds. Though this may not be able to supply the volumes required for Pycasso or other hypothetical CCS Transport & Storage projects, it is expected that the skills that do exist are highly transferable to the Operations and Maintenance phase of the transport component of CCS.

3.6 Results – Germany

The results for Germany are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
Delta Rhine Corridor	Insufficient information	Onshore Pipeline	N/A	Insufficient information	2030
H2morrow	Blue Hydrogen	Onshore Pipeline	Greenfield	2	2030
H2GE Rostock	Blue Hydrogen	Both	Brownfield	2	2029

There are currently no planned, full value chain CCS projects planned in Germany. The CO₂ captured in Germany is planned to be transported to and stored in the Norwegian North Sea. As a result, storage estimates have not been included in Germany's value chain estimates. It is assumed that these employment estimates will have been captured in the planned storage sites in Norway. Based on desk-based research into these projects, it is expected that both projects will utilise repurposed onshore pipelines and H2GE Rostock will also utilise logistical solutions. The peaks expected in 2027 and 2031 are expected to be driven by the repurposing of the expected onshore pipelines for H2morrow and H2GE Rostock and the German section of the Delta Rhine Corridor.

As the pipelines for the H2morrow and H2GE Rostock projects are both expected to be repurposed, it is expected that the vast majority of jobs will be involved in engineering professions and management. Civil engineers, mechanical engineers, senior civil construction managers and a few other people from the Management job family, e.g. project manager, are expected to account for most of these roles. The ratio between civil engineering roles/construction roles and management roles is expected to be around 70:30. Excluding jobs in the Development and Consenting phases, the civil engineering/construction roles are expected to support between **160** and **180** jobs between the two peaks and management is expected to require between 70 and **80** roles between the two peaks. Building of the vessels that will transport CO₂ from H2GE Rostock is expected to be in line with other logistics projects.

Once operational, around 100 people will be required to operate and maintain the onshore pipeline infrastructure and ships for these two projects. In line with other projects pursuing these transport solutions, a high proportion of the people and skills required will be found in the Asset Operations and Marine job families. The onshore pipelines will likely require a range of skilled maintenance technicians. The vessels carrying the CO₂ to the Norwegian North Sea will likely create opportunities for deck operators, quayside operatives, seafarers, skippers, harbour masters, Health & Safety officers and additional deck crew.

However, it is the substantial work required for the 315km (approximately) German arm of the cross-border Delta Rhine Corridor project. At peak, this project alone could see as many as **2000** jobs being needed. Around half of these jobs will be involved in the civil engineering, requiring civil and mechanical engineers as well as a range of other skilled and semi-skilled roles for the Mechanical job family. Most other jobs will be accounted for by management roles, semi-skilled and manual roles (for pipelaying) and other equipment and machinery handling roles. Whilst the extent of the machinery and equipment use is uncertain, it is likely that for large-scale projects such as the Delta-Rhine Corridor, these solutions will play a larger role. As a result, it would be reasonable to expect that the extent of the employment forecast in the graph may be reduced. However, as the scale of the machinery required is difficult to estimate, the workforce ratios used for other, smaller projects were kept.

The lack of available data around Germany's oil and gas sector has made estimating the numerical potential for skills transferability very challenging. Combined with the lack of a confirmed complete CCS value chain, providing a robust, specific estimate is nearly impossible. However, the German government has recently launched proposals that set out a decarbonisation strategy that integrates CCS. As a result, it is very likely that the demand for people and skills will rise, meeting the requirements of a growing pipeline. Germany's oil and gas extraction sector, most recently estimated to employ between **1000** and **1500** people, is following the common trend of declining production. As this trend continues, future CCS value

chains in Germany may be needed to accommodate for this. This view has been further validated through industry engagement. According to a leading German oil and gas developer, there is definite potential in cross-sector skills transferability. Despite challenges, including the higher on-average wages offered by oil and gas and the demand pressures created by the significant investment in sectors that also require legacy oil and gas skills (i.e. renewables), social value perceptions are believed to be an increasingly influencing factor. Specifically, the positive social value perception of CCS, compared to the negative social value perception of oil and gas has resulted in a growing desire to transfer to the former. Though it may be difficult to predict what a potential expansion of CCS in Germany may look like, especially when considering the labour supply impacts of renewable energy producing projects, the relevant skill base and social desire to transition to CCS is in place.

3.7 Results – Greece

The results for Greece are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
Prinos	-Cement -Refinery	Logistics	Greenfield	3.5 - 4	2025

Prinos CCS, Greece's only CCS project in the planned project pipeline, expects to capture between 350-400 million tonnes equivalent of CO₂ for nearby emitter industries. At present, three industries are expected to be connected to the Prinos project, including a refinery and two cement factories. Above is the estimated employment based on the Transport & Storage solutions chosen for the project.

As demonstrated above, Greece's expected long-term Transport & Storage employment is not expected to be as high compared to the workforces of other countries. Peaking at **150** jobs in 2024, employment is estimated to drop off as Prinos CCS – currently Greece's sole CCS project – enters commercial operation, bringing an end to the development of the storage facility and the four CO₂ transport vessels. Additional construction may yet take place. Although the present transport solution is liquified CO₂ being carried on carrier ships, there is still potential for an additional pipeline to be built. However, since this has yet to be confirmed, no job estimates have been made. Current estimates place the operational date towards the end of 2025 or the beginning of 2026. On average, it is expected that between **60 to 80 people** will be needed to operate and maintain compression stations, injection pumps, valves and other major components at the CO₂ storage site. As with other major offshore projects, the FTEs (full time equivalent) associated with the O&M phase will inevitably be smaller once factoring in shift patterns. During

the Operations & Maintenance phase, there will also be an expected **22 to 30 people** operating the four transport vessels carrying the liquified CO₂. Important to note is that the existence of off-site jobs that typically take place in an office environment (e.g. Office Manager, Financial Controller, Corporate Manager) are what make up the difference between the job estimates present in the graph and the job estimates described here. For the operating and maintaining the vessels and storage site itself, it is expected that an additional three jobs and ten jobs respectively take place in a corporate environment. For calculating the potential job reductions linked to anticipated improvements in productivity and technology, the point at which they come into effect has been assumed to be similar to the UK's CCS industry. On the one hand, Greece's project pipeline is not as large as countries like the UK or Norway – only one project is planned. On the other hand, it is expected that this project will enter commercial operations several years before the UK's projects, meaning the opportunity to learn, improve, become more efficient and utilise innovative technological solutions will come sooner. Therefore, for the purposes of this forecast, the point at which these factors come into effect has been estimated at around 2031.

Estimates for the size of Greece's oil and gas sector are not readily available. Based on the industry engagement and the amount produced, it is likely that the oil and gas operations workforce includes a few thousand people. Despite this, the foundations for cross-sector transferability are strong. As confirmed through industry engagement, the oil and gas workforce shares many of the same processes required by CCS Transport & Storage. Drilling and injecting, transporting liquified CO₂ and designing and constructing the ships, which themselves have highly standardised designs used by both sectors, involve many specialised skills required by CCS. The influence of social value perceptions, and how they differ between oil and gas and CCS is also playing a significant factor. Likely to be the main challenge for this transition is the workforce requirements. It is expected that in the future, CCS may require more roles than oil and gas. As a result, Greece's future CCS supply chain is likely to require some recruitment outside of CCS. However, given the lack of available data on Greece's oil and gas sector, estimating the extent is not currently possible.

3.8 Results – Italy

The results for Italy are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
Ravenna	-Cement -Ceramics -Chemicals -Steel -Waste to energy	Onshore Pipeline	Brownfield	Phase 1: 0.025 Phase 2: 4	Phase 1: 2024 Phase 2: 2027

Similar to Greece, Italy's CCS pipeline is limited to a single project – the Raveena CCS hub. Currently in a test phase, aiming to capture 25,000 tonnes of CO₂ from Eni's natural gas processing plant in Raveena, it's anticipated CO₂ capacity is expected to be staggered across at least two phases; Phase 1 allowing for 25000 tonnes to be stored per year from next year, Phase 2 allowing for 4 million from 2027, and a third phase, storing a possible 16 million tonnes from 2030 onwards. However, the third phase largely depends on future market demand and is therefore not yet a confirmed upgrade in storage capacity. This project is expected to support a steady pipeline of workers in the Operations & Maintenance of the project lifecycle, especially at the storage site itself in the Adriatic Sea and the offshore pipeline it connects to. The **60** expected jobs supported are likely to be relatively evenly split across a wide range of job families and job family sub groups. Typical skilled operative roles will likely include asset, civil construction, subsea and mechanical operatives, amounting to potentially a third of this annual workforce. Management, HSEQ and Drilling/Wells will likely account for most other roles. However, if a hypothetical third phase is explored and a quadrupling in storage capacity is realised, the opportunities for future employment expansion could be substantial.

Data around the size of Italy's oil and gas industry is limited. The most recently released data, dating employment up until 2020, suggests that there are roughly **1750** employees working in the country's oil and natural gas extraction sector. As a result, estimating the transferability of people and skills from this sector into CCS Transport & Storage is challenging. Skills wise, the opportunities for cross-sector transition are strong; Eni and Snam, Raveena CCS's Transport & Storage developers, are energy companies with decades worth of experience in oil and gas extraction practices. By integrating CCS Transport & Storage into their portfolio of economic activities, the potential for the transition of people and skills is very high, especially when current estimates indicate relatively low levels of employment.

3.9 Results – Netherlands

The results for the Netherlands are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
Aramis Hub	-Cement -Chemicals -Refineries -Steel -Waste incinerators	Onshore Pipeline	Brownfield	5	2027
Delta Rhine Corridor	Insufficient information	Onshore Pipeline	N/A	Insufficient information	2030
Neptune Energy L10	-Oil & Gas	Both	Brownfield	5	2028
Porthos CO T&S 2	-Chemicals -Oil & Gas -Refinery	Onshore Pipeline	Brownfield	2.5	2026

The Dutch CCS Transport & Storage employment pipeline draws many similarities to the pipelines projected for Croatia and Greece. As is the case with these two countries, the Construction phase is expected to peak just short of **3400** jobs in the mid-2020s, ready for planned commercial operations between 2026 and 2030. This peak is likely to be higher than those expected in Croatia and Greece because it is assumed that the onshore pipeline infrastructure will be new builds, rather than repurposed. As much as half of all peak transport jobs (around **1200** jobs) are likely to be in the Technical job family, mostly comprised of civil and mechanical engineers. The second largest proportion of peak transport employment will be involved in the laying and overall assembly of the pipeline networks. This will likely involve a large

number of skilled, semi-skilled and manual roles from the Civil Construction job family. Typical roles include supervisors, steel fixers, drivers, heavy machinery operators and other ground workers. Health & Safety, quality control and environmental officers will likely also be required at this stage. In total, this proportion is estimated to require between **500 to 700** people.

The storage peak will likely require around **830** roles. As is expected of all projects, the workforce required to construct and assemble the offshore storage infrastructure is likely to involve a more diverse range of skills. In addition to the Technical, Civil Construction and HSEQ roles expected, a large number of jobs from the Mechanical and Drilling/Wells job families will likely be needed. From the Mechanical job family, management roles (e.g. senior mechanical technicians, supervisors) and semi-skilled operatives (e.g. fitters, mechanics) are likely to be required. The bulk of Drilling/Wells jobs will likely be skilled workover, drilling and field engineers. However, the list of possible roles required in the Construction phase of the storage infrastructure is extensive and varied; roles in the Facilities, Marine and Subsea job families are likely to also be needed.

Once operational, employment will flatten at around **200** jobs per year. As is the case with most CCS Transport & Storage projects, a large volume of these jobs will relate to the Asset Operations job family. For transport, which is expected to reach around **120** jobs per year, it is expected that skilled, semi-skilled and manual operatives (e.g. maintenance technicians and mechanics) will account for the bulk of employment required. This will likely account for around **70 to 90 roles**. The rest of the jobs will be split between Asset Management/Leadership, Health & Safety and ongoing corporate service roles linked to the organisation overseeing the project. Similar ratios can be expected for the offshore infrastructure. Due to the more hazardous offshore conditions, a slightly higher proportion of jobs will be created by Health & Safety and Control Room officers.

The Netherlands is one of Europe's largest producers of oil and natural gas. Since exploration began around 50 years ago, over 250 gas fields and 15 oil wells have entered and remained in production. Since 2019, where the Dutch government announced that domestic gas production would be halted by the end of the decade and the country would be gas free by 2050, production has quickly fallen. As is the case with most, if not all countries in this study, this has led to a shrinking oil and gas workforce. The most recent estimates suggest the oil and gas extraction workforce employs around **2500** people. However, given that the most recent estimates date back to 2021, it is likely that this figure is lower. By coupling the planned accelerated decline of production with the planned development of a CCS industry, there are strong opportunities for cross-sector transferability. As exploration and production is on the decline, it is likely that the majority of these jobs will be found in the Asset Operations and Drilling/Wells job families. The skills involved in these job families, mainly asset managers, maintenance technicians, painters, control room operators and wells/completions engineers have direct application to the Operations and Maintenance phase of CCS. Average annual job reductions in oil and gas since its most recent peak in 2015 have amounted to around **240** jobs per year. Operations and Maintenance jobs in CCS are not currently expected to exceed **150** per year (260 including Corporate Services roles), these reductions have the numerical potential to address a significant proportion of the expected Operations and Maintenance workforce in CCS.

For peak construction, estimating transferability is challenging. Since offshore drilling in the Netherlands is being curtailed, there is likely no significant workforce dedicated in the oil and gas Civil Construction. Therefore, any transferability for the Construction phase will likely involve skills from employees involved in older oil and gas projects.

3.10 Results – Norway

The results for Norway are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
Aker BP Poseidon	-Oil and gas processing -Power and heat -Metal processing -Cement/glass	N/A	Brownfield	5	2030
Borg CO₂	Insufficient info (excluded from estimates)	Insufficient info (excluded from estimates)	Insufficient info (excluded from estimates)	0.5	Insufficient info (excluded from estimates)
Equinor Smeaheia	- Oil & gas transmission	Logistics	Greenfield	20	2028
Horisont Energi Errai	-Ammonia -Hydrogen	Onshore Pipeline	Greenfield	8	2026
Northern Lights (1&2), Longship	-Biofuels -Cement -Steel -Waste-to-energy	Both	Greenfield	5	2024
Polaris	-Ammonia	Logistics	Greenfield	3	2029
Sleipner	-Natural gas processing	Onshore Pipeline	Greenfield	1	1996
Snohvit	-Natural gas processing	Onshore Pipeline	Greenfield	1	2008
Trudvang	Insufficient information	N/A (receives liquified CO ₂ via shipping)	Greenfield	9	2029
Wintershall Dea Havstjerne	Insufficient information	N/A (receives liquified CO ₂ via shipping)	Greenfield	8	2028
Wintershall Dea Luna	Oil and gas processing	N/A (receives liquified CO ₂ via shipping)	Greenfield	5	2030

Norway has one of the largest CCS Transport & Storage pipelines in Europe. This is expected to drive a prolonged employment peak between 2024 and 2029. Of the **1400 to 1900** jobs expected to be required between now and the end of the decade, around 85% of them are likely to be created in supporting the Construction phase of the offshore storage infrastructure. A key driver for this growth is the longer than average distance between the shore and the storage sites, ranging from 100 to 150km in distance. At peak, the Construction of pipelines with lengths between 100km and 150km will range from **400 to 700 jobs**. The proportions will likely be similar to offshore pipelines of archetypal size; skilled subsea operatives, semi-skilled and manual civil construction operatives, civil engineers, marine engineers, offshore vessel drivers and Health & Safety officers will all be involved in these pipelines' construction and assembly. The sheer length of the pipelines, in addition to the storage sites themselves, will also require significantly higher numbers of maintenance technicians and mechanics. These distances will require a higher number of Health & Safety officers and offshore vessel drivers as well. Resultingly, offshore storage infrastructure may require in excess of **300** jobs throughout the first half of the next decade. Combined with the maintenance work for the onshore infrastructure, the operations crew required for the CO₂ carrying ships and the regular corporate service activities expected offsite, employment may exceed **500** jobs per year once all estimated projects enter commercial operation.

Construction of the ships and onshore infrastructure will also generate higher than average levels of employment. Many of these jobs, of which **500** are expected to be required in the next two years, will belong to the Technical, Civil Construction, Management, Mechanical and Marine job families. Once operational, employment is expected to decline at around **120** jobs per annum. Logistical solutions, estimated to account for an average of **90** jobs are assumed to require the typical makeup of skills from the Marine & Ports job family. The remaining jobs assumed to be supported during this phase will likely be made up of maintenance technicians, civil engineers, mechanical engineers, site managers and corporate service staff based off-site.

As by far Europe's largest producer of oil and gas, Norway offers strong foundations on which a cross-sector transition to CCS can take place. By recent estimates, there are around **200000** people directly and indirectly employed by Norway's petroleum sector. Estimates for Norway's natural gas sector are not available, but this would likely push this number up. Jobs in the Drilling/Wells and Asset Operations are, based on the very similar activities and practices involved in both industries, the job families that will likely account for the highest volume of directly transferable skills. Though difficult to estimate, these job families could be in excess of 50,000 jobs. Since the Operations & Maintenance phases for Norway's CSS Transport & Storage sector is expected to account for less than 1% of this figure, the oil and gas sector does have the capacity to accommodate for a cross-sector transition, even if additional CCS and other renewable energy projects are announced.

3.11 Results – UK

The results for the UK are as follows.

Project	Type of Emitter Industries	Transport Type	Storage Type	CO ₂ Capacity per Year (Mts)	Operational Year
Acorn	-Biomass -Energy from Waste -Hydrogen -Power	Onshore Pipeline	Greenfield & Brownfield	20	2036
Hynet	-Hydrogen	Onshore Pipeline	Brownfield	1	2029
Morecambe Cluster	-Cement & Lime	Onshore Pipeline	Brownfield	4	2036
Northern Endurance	-Cement & Lime -Chemicals -Energy from Waste and Biofuel -Glass -Iron & Steel -Refining	Onshore Pipeline	Greenfield & Brownfield	10	2031
7CO₂	-Biomass -Cement	Both	None	4	2038
Solent Cluster	-Blue Hydrogen -Green Hydrogen Waste to Methanol -Waste to Aviation Fuel (SAF)	Onshore Pipeline	Greenfield	10	2038

South Wales Cluster	-Cement	Both	None	16	2037
	-Insulation				
	-General manufacturing				
	-Paper				
	-Power				
Viking	-Steel & metals				
	-Oil & Gas	Onshore Pipeline	Brownfield	10	2029
-Ports					

Eight cluster projects are currently in the pipeline for industrial decarbonisation and CCS in the UK. With one of the largest project pipelines in Europe, it is expected that employment across the UK will be very high.. There are two employment peaks currently expected between now and 2050, corresponding to the significant amount of construction required to accommodate for the 'Track 1' and 'Track 2' projects. Track 1, which includes Hynet, Northern Endurance (or Net Zero Teesside) and Viking (or Humber Zero) are estimated to be the largest cluster projects, requiring close to a peak of over **2200** jobs collectively to develop and assemble or modernise the Transport & Storage infrastructure. Track 2 projects, comprised of Acorn (or Scottish Cluster), Morecambe Net Zero Cluster, 7CO₂, Solent Cluster and the South Wales Cluster, are expected to reach an even higher peak of over **2400** jobs by 2050.

Typical job family and job family sub group proportions would apply to the UK. During the two construction peaks, the skills base is expected to be very wide. At these peaks, where the offshore infrastructure will be assembled, hundreds of jobs from the Drilling/Wells, Technical, Mechanical, Civil Construction, Marine, Subsea and Marine job families will be required. Though the skills types will be in line with projects in other countries, the scale for this Construction phase will be substantial. Likewise, the size of the pipeline is such that the required number of jobs for the Operations & Maintenance phase for each project is much higher than the average of most

countries, even exceeding **1000** jobs in 2039. Similar, because of the wide range of different transport and storage types, the skills composition is likely to be very diverse. This will include hundreds of maintenance technicians, civil engineers, mechanical engineers, completions engineers, skilled and semi-skilled mechanics, Health & Safety officers and significant management teams.

The UK's oil and gas workforce is substantial, owing to its extensive legacy in hydrocarbon exploration in the North Sea. By current estimates, there are over **122000** direct and indirect jobs in this sector. By 2030, as a just transition takes place, this figure is expected to fall to around **87000** jobs. With a projected reduction of **35000** jobs, there are significant opportunities for CCS transition, even if the current CCS project pipeline was to expand significantly. Of this reduction figure, it is expected that **6000** jobs in the Drilling/Wells job family, **7000** in the Technical job family, **3000** in the Asset Operations job family, **2500** from Management and **1500** from Mechanical may be freed up. These job families account for most of the major skills required by CCS and other clean energy sectors in the future. The expansion of offshore wind, onshore wind, solar, nuclear energy and other sectors will likely require a high proportion of these jobs. However, given the especially close alignment and sheer size of the change, the prospect of a transition from oil and gas into CCS is very promising.

4 Analysis and Conclusions

The findings section suggests that, overall, CCS Transport & Storage can support **13360** jobs across all of the ten countries' peak years. As is expected, these employment spikes are consistently driven by the substantial technical requirements of the Construction phase of each project. This also includes assembly. Across seven of the ten countries, these Construction phase spikes are driven by the storage infrastructure, rather than by transport. This is unsurprising. Firstly, the construction or repurposing of offshore pipeline presents more logistical challenges than for onshore transport pipelines. The demand for specialised transport vessels for offshore workers is on a scale not typically required by onshore pipeline projects. Secondly, working offshore inevitably involves more risks to health and safety. Hazardous offshore conditions therefore require many more officers and roles from the Health & Safety job family, including safety engineers, health and safety planners and emergency response personnel. Thirdly, the specialised engineering and installation requirements of offshore pipeline are such that more highly skilled roles are required when compared with onshore pipelines. As a result, more skilled and semi-skilled operatives from the Marine and Subsea job families are required. Furthermore, the harsher marine environment is such that the overall engineering and installation requirements are much more labour-intensive than for onshore. Overall, the fact that most of the projects analysed for each country are utilising offshore, rather than onshore solutions, suggests not only an alignment of storage strategy, but also that future employment peaks for each country are likely to be dramatic.

There is clear alignment in the overall employment profiles. As demonstrated in the table below, it is expected that much of the activity expected to take place by 2040 will likely take place towards the end of the 2020s. Beyond 2030, employment across the studied countries remains static, with the UK being the sole exception. The reason for this exception is the time gap between the Track 1 and Track 2 CCS projects, whereby several projects are not expected to enter commercial operations until the mid-2030s. This demonstrates a few things. Firstly, it demonstrates how the broad industrial decarbonisation strategies being pursued in these countries are relatively aligned. Clearly, rapidly upscaling the capacity for industrial emissions to be captured, transported and stored is a common component in the ten countries' decarbonisation strategies. Comparing the current project pipeline against JRC scenarios would suggest this is also consistent across the whole of Europe.

Despite several commonalities across the ten countries, there are also differences. The employment range is very wide. Where some countries are expected to have peak workforce numbers between 150 and 200, other countries, like the Belgium, the Netherlands, Norway and the UK are expected to produce jobs in the thousands. This highlights the centrality of geography. Each of these four countries have direct access to the North Sea. The North Sea in particular provides wider CCS Transport & Storage opportunities compared to the Mediterranean, including the rich geological diversity, shallower waters and significant legacy infrastructure and resulting expertise in oil and gas. As a result, it is not surprising that such a wide employment range exists. It also highlights how, from a volumetric perspective, the potential for a large-scale just transition is perhaps more promising for North Sea bordering countries.

Although measuring exact pipeline length is not within the scope of this study, the confirmed pipelines assessed for this study are not believed to come close to matching the forecasted pipelines suggested by the JRC scenarios, including Scenario D2, the study's smallest scenario. By applying the methodology for producing the job estimates of Section 3 to JRC's pipeline length scenarios, we estimate that between **1550** and **1950** jobs could be required for the Operations & Maintenance phase of the onshore pipeline infrastructure required across the various JDC scenarios. Inevitably, this figure will be considerably higher if factoring in offshore pipeline infrastructure. By contrast, the actual findings of Section 3 indicate that between **650** and **700** jobs (logistics jobs removed) would likely in Operations & Maintenance in 2030. At first glance, this study's estimates are roughly 40% the size of those that the JRC scenarios would indicate. This is no surprising. Afterall, the JRC onshore pipeline scenarios, ranging from 6000km (Scenario D2) to 7200km (Scenario C1), imply a significant expansion of CO₂ Transport & Storage infrastructure.

Scenario	2030			2040		
	Onshore (km)	Offshore (km)	Jobs (Onshore only)	Onshore (km)	Offshore (km)	Jobs (Onshore only)
A1	6000	700	1750	13800	1600	4050
A2	5900	800	1750	13600	1800	4000
A3	5900	800	1750	13600	1800	4000
B1	6700	600	1950	17400	1300	5100
B2	6000	700	1750	14300	1600	4200
C1	6500	700	1900	14200	1500	4200
D1	5600	900	1650	7400	1400	2200
D2	5200	800	1550	7500	1200	2200

Table above: JCD Scenarios. As the maximum number of sinks was assumed (58 offshore sinks (by 2040) identified in JRC report), it was not possible to estimate the offshore pipeline length for 2030. As a result, only onshore pipeline and jobs were calculated

However, there are a number of differences between this study and the JRC study that would account for this. Firstly, the pipeline infrastructure that underpinned the calculations for Section 3 was estimated on a project-by-project basis. Onshore pipeline distances, estimated either through desk-based research or using industry averages (53km), refer to the infrastructure for transporting CO₂ from the capture sites at the emitter industries to the point at which it would then be transported offshore. By contrast, the JRC onshore pipeline scenarios refer to the complete, interconnected network of pipes expected to be operational on land. These networks are cross-border and often stretch across entire countries, linked various CCS projects with each other. As a result, more jobs will be required for the Operations & Maintenance of these interconnected networks.

Secondly the scope of this study was such that only ten countries were examined. By contrast, the JRC report explored the pipeline network scenarios across Europe, including over 20 countries. Inevitably, much more pipeline will be required, especially by countries with significant geological potential, such as Spain. Even countries with fewer potential onshore sinks, such as Czech Republic and Latvia, may require large workforces to connect the storage sites to the wider Europe network. It is therefore not surprising that the workforce estimates based on the JRC study are more than double the estimates produced for this report.

The final factor is likely to be the most significant factor in explaining the difference between the JRC report and this study. The scope of this study was such only confirmed projects have been accounted for. Even among the projects included as part of this study, there is no single, regularly updated, authoritative, pan-European pipeline that exists. By contrast, the JRC scenarios for 2040 suggest a substantial increase in Transport & Storage infrastructure. In most cases (all except scenarios D1 and D2), Europe's onshore CO₂ pipeline networks are expected to more than double in length, and by an average of around 12000km. Based on these scenarios, the job demand for Operations & Maintenance would rise from between **1550** (D2) and **1950** (B1) jobs to between **2200** (D1 and D2) and **5100** (B1) jobs. In terms of jobs, this would represent a job increase percentage range of 30% and 57%. According to this study, between **700** and **750** will be required for the Operation & Maintenance in 2040. Clearly, the gap between the JRC scenarios and this study's 2040 estimates is fundamentally different. However, this difference can largely be explained by lack of a project pipeline much beyond 2030. Though not confirmed, it is likely that decarbonisation across Europe will result in an expansion of CCS projects in the 2030s also. As a result, significantly more employment will be required for the Operations & Maintenance of the onshore infrastructure. As this study is based purely on demand, it relies only on the availability of publicly available project data.

Further study, perhaps using CO₂ storage capacity targets, would advance this study's finding further. Nevertheless, when combining the project pipeline factor with the other two previously identified, then there is a strong case for these findings for onshore infrastructure to be used in conjunction with each other. Based on the differing methodologies employed by each report, the employment gaps revealed appear very plausible. For 2030, a simple expansion in the countries being examined, combined with the greater focus on network interconnectivity, could satisfactorily account for this gap. The lack of project pipeline post-2040, a factor less significant for the 2030 gap, goes for in explaining why this gap widens. Therefore, in the context of the JRC scenarios, there is strong evidence to suggest that an upscaling in the work completed for this study would align well with the JRC scenarios.

This is more difficult to determine for offshore storage infrastructure. As with onshore, the JCD scenarios measure the offshore pipeline network. However, as this study has had to assume the 'storage' related jobs include both the sites and the offshore pipeline, forecasting employment for the latter only would present a significant challenge at a scenario-by scenario-level. By employing the same methodology to the JRC report, over **2200** Operations & Maintenance jobs could be supported in 2040. This would assume the existence of a maximum of 58 offshore CO₂ sinks, each with four subsea wells. By this study's estimates, around **1250** jobs in the Operations & Maintenance phase could be supported. By considering the factors detailed above, this gap seems reasonable. However, the difference in each report's offshore storage project pipeline is such that comparing them would be challenging. There may be several reasons for this difference, including perceived uncertainties in the JRC report around the ability for UK storage sites to be situated on EU waters. As a potentially major market for CO₂, differing approaches to their inclusion in employment forecasts would have significant impacts on employment.

Appendix A: Assumptions

The following assumptions have been made during the course of this research and analysis:

- All employment information (figures, durations) for each phase have been taken directly through external engagement, desk-based research, and some in-house expertise. A full breakdown of all the companies consulted in support of this study can be found in Appendix B.
- Employment can be fit into five broad categories: Development, Manufacturing, Construction, Operations & Maintenance and Corporate Services. This was established through various internal and external expert discussions.
- For the purposes of this study, manufacturing jobs will not be included. There are several reasons for this. Firstly, as much of the transport infrastructure is legacy, the present manufacturing job estimates will likely be low. This also makes them difficult to estimate/stakeholders may not have access to this information.
- Two broad methods of transportation have been assumed: onshore pipeline and logistics. Whilst these were initially identified through desk-based research, this was validated through industry engagement.
- Two methods of storing carbon have been identified: greenfield and brownfield sites. Whilst these were initially identified through desk-based research, this was also validated through industry engagement. For the purposes of this study, greenfield sites and brownfield sites have been used to refer to saline aquifers and depleted oil or gas fields respectively.
- The ONS definition was used to calculate indirect employment.
- ONS was used to calculate the difference between FTEs and Jobs. This study calculates the latter.
- Storing carbon at greenfield sites occurs five years before storage at brownfield sites. This assumption was reached following consultation with industry stakeholders (see list in first assumption).
- The project pipelines for each country were developed through industry research. Although the operational dates of some projects may be subject to change, the dates have been taken as last updated.
- It has been assumed that there will be people working in corporate roles during all phases and stages involved in each cluster. This conclusion was reached since each project will require leadership and corporate support throughout its lifespan.
- A twenty-year lifespan has been assumed for each project. However, improved operations and maintenance technologies may extend these.

- Some projects have confirmed lifecycles longer than 20 years. Norwegian projects and some of the projects linked to Norway have been anticipated to be operational for as many as 50 years.
- Desk-based research has been undertaken to fill in any information gaps that are needed for main calculations.
- All relevant information for each project has been collected either through industry engagement or through desk-based research.
- Anticipated annual employment reductions as a result of improvements in productivity & efficiency as well as gains in technological advancement is expected to be at 1.25% and 2.5% respectively. As CCS is a relatively immature industry, it is expected that any gains in efficiency, productivity and technology will continue to be larger before maturing.
- Since it is a nascent industry, the improvement factors around productivity, efficiency and technological advancements have been assumed as the same as floating offshore wind - another nascent industry.
- For pipeline transport methods, ratios were provided in confidence by ArcelorMittal and BP. For estimating transport for a 1.5 MtCO₂ project, 4.6 FTEs (including management) is needed per km of pipe. If repurposing a pipe, this figure falls to 3.1.
- For an archetypal storage project (or sink), it is assumed that four subsea wells will be developed. This archetype was provided by BP.
- Whilst it is likely that the employment required to construct/repurpose a pipe that can transport a higher amount of CO₂, the difference is not significant enough for this to be scaled. Thus, regardless of pipe diameter, employment per km of pipe is kept the same.
- In the absence of specific offshore pipeline length data, an industry average of 20km has been assumed. This archetypal figure was provided by BP.
- In the absence of specific onshore pipeline length data, an industry average of 53km has been assumed. This archetypal figure was found through desk-based research. Looking at five different CCS projects across Europe that had confirmed pipeline lengths, the onshore pipeline ranged from 30km to 88km.
- In the absence of data on the number of vessels for logistical solutions, four vessels have been assumed.
- Where Oil & Gas estimates are available and the industries are, like the UK, in decline, the Energy Skills Intelligence Hub (ESIH) was used. This was used to calculate ratios between Oil & Gas and CCS employment before being broken down by job family or job family sub group.
- Where there are projects with phased expansions in capacity over time, the earliest of these dates is assumed to be first point of commercial operation and all other Development and Construction activities will be in place. In reality it is likely these will be spread out.

Appendix B: Opergy Common People & Skills Taxonomy

This appendix provides details of the Opergy Common People & Skills Taxonomy, categorising the typical roles within the energy sector into groups or 'families' of similar skills sets.

Job Family	Job Family Sub Group	Typical Role(s)
Management	Corporate Leadership	Company Board roles, Company Directors, C Suite roles etc...
	Management Corporate	Head of..., Senior Vice President, Director in Title etc...
	Management Operational	Head of..., Senior Vice President, Director in Title etc...
	Project Management	Senior Responsible Officer, Programme Manager, Project Manager
	Project Engineering	Project Engineer / Project Controller / Project Supervisor / Operational Licensing & Regulations
Technical	Technical - Mechanical Engineer	Mechanical Engineer, Piping Engineer, Pipeline Engineer
	Technical - Electrical Engineer	Electrical Engineer
	Technical - Structural Engineer/Surveyor	Naval Architect, Structural Engineer, Architect, Surveyor
	Technical - Civil Engineer/Drilling Engineer/Surveyor	Civil Engineer, Drilling/Reservoir Engineer, Quantity Surveyor, Surveyor
	Technical - Geological Scientist/Surveyor/Engineer	Geotechnical Eng / Hydrographic Surveyor / Geo Scientist / Oceanographer / Geologist / Environmentalist / Geo & Spatial Information specialist
	Technical - Chemical Engineer	Nuclear engineer, Hydrogen engineer, Battery engineer
	Technical - Process Engineer	Process Engineer, Data Engineer, Improvement Engineer
	Technical - Instrument Engineer	Instrument Eng, E&I Eng, Controls Eng, Test Eng, Fire and Gas Eng, Commissioning Eng
	Technical - Support	Draughtsperson, CAD Operator, CAD Technician, Designer, Certification Engineer
Professional	Professional - Medical	Doctors, Paramedics
	Professional - Consultant	Senior Consultants / Associate Consultants / Consultants
	Professional - Audit	Auditor
Consenting & Project Planning	Planning/Development Management	Manager of consenting operations, Consenting Project Manager etc...
	Senior Specialist/Lead Adviser	Responsible for consenting policy/strategy, lead for Environmental Impact Assessments etc...

Job Family	Job Family Sub Group	Typical Role(s)
	Specialist/Adviser	Supporting consenting policy/strategy, specialist advice on Environmental Impact Assessments
	Stakeholder Management	Management of engagement with public, political and statutory stakeholders etc...
	Land Management	Negotiating/setting up agreements for and purchase of land
Corporate Services	Corporate Services - Human Resources (HR)	Advisor, Partner, Manager etc...
	Corporate Services - Information Technology (IT)	Helpdesk Technician, Software, Hardware etc...
	Corporate Services - Finance	Accountant, Bookkeeper, General Ledger Clerk etc...
	Corporate Services - Legal	Lawyer, Consenting Counsel, General Counsel, Legal Advisor, Paralegal etc...
	Corporate Services - General	Office Manager, Facilities Manager, Real Estate Manager etc...
	Corporate Services - Project Support Office	Project Coordinator, PMO, Project Planner, Project Scheduler, Document Cost/Controllers
	Corporate Services - Administration	PA, Secretary, Executive Assistant etc...
HSEQ	Health & Safety	Advisor, Partner, Manager, Safety Engineer etc...
	Quality	Advisor, Partner, Manager etc...
	Environmental	ESG Manager, Advisor, Partner, Manager etc...
People Development	People Development & Skills Graduate	Trainer, Teacher, instructor etc...
	Trainee/Intern	Career stage - Various trades
	Apprentice	Career stage - Various trades
		Career stage - Various trades
Commercial	Sales	Sales Manager, BD Manager, Sales Executive etc...
	Marketing	Marketing Executive, Marketing Mgr, Communications Mgr, Publicity Mgr etc...
	Contracts & Commercial	Commercial Executive, Commercial Manger, etc...
	Procurement	Buyer, Procurement Officer, Supply Chain Mgr etc...
Facilities	Catering, Cleaning & Security	Chef, Cook, Cleaner, Security guard
	Facility Maintenance	Builder, plumber, painter, handyman etc...
	Air & Marine Coordination	HLO coordinator, Marine Coordinator
	Logistics	Crane Driver, Forklift Driver etc...
Drilling/Wells	Drilling Superintendent / Rig Manager	Drilling Supervisor, Maintenance Superintendent, Offshore Installation Manager
	Well / Completions Engineer	Workover, Drilling, Field Engineer
	Semi-Skilled drilling / wells	Derrickman
	Manual drilling / wells	Roustabout, Floor hand
Civil Construction	Civil Construction Senior/Management	Site Manager, Construction Project Mgr, Construction Contracts Mgr, Production Mgrs.
	Skilled Civil Construction Operatives	Supervisor, Ganger, Appointed Person etc...
	Semi-Skilled Civil Construction Operatives	Concrete Ops, Steelfixer, Plant Op, Driver, Crane Op, Slinger/Signaller, Scaffolder, Painter, Access Rigger etc...

Job Family	Job Family Sub Group	Typical Role(s)
	Manual Civil Construction Operatives	Labourer, Groundworker
Fabrication Yards	Fabrication Yard Senior/Management	Field Service Manager, Senior Fabrication Manager, Team Lead etc...
	Skilled Fabrication Yard Operatives	Fabricator, Fitter, Welder, Pipefitter etc...
	Semi-Skilled Fabrication Yard Operatives	Crane Op, Slinger/Signaller, Plant Operator, Site Stores, Scaffolder, Rigger, Rope access tech, Painter etc...
	Manual Fabrication Yard Operatives	Labourer, Helper etc...
Factories & Manufacturing	Factories & Manufacturing Senior/Management	Supervisor, Shift Manager, Foreman, Operations Coordinator, Team Lead etc...
	Skilled Factories & Manufacturing Operatives	Inspection, Installation Tech, Welder, Plater, Pipefitter, Machinst etc...
	Semi-Skilled Factories & Manufacturing Operatives	Production Operative, Plant Operator, Site Stores, Driver, Painter, Blaster etc...
	Manual Factories & Manufacturing Operatives	Labourer, etc...
Asset Operators	Asset Senior/Management	Supervisor, Commissioning Supervisor, Control room Supervisor etc...
	Skilled Asset Operators	Control Room Operator, Plant Operators, etc...
	Semi-Skilled Asset Operators	Scaffolder, Rigger, Rope access tech, Painter etc...
	Manual Asset Operators	Labourer, Helper etc...
Electrical	Electrical Senior/Management	Electrical Supervisor, Electrical SAP, HV authorised person, Senior Electrical/Electronic Tech
	Skilled Electrical	Electrical Technician, Electrician, Electronic Tech, Electrical Fitter
	Semi-Skilled Electrical	Cable Jointer etc...
	Manual Electrical	Cable puller, labourer etc...
Mechanical	Mechanical Senior/Management	Senior Mechanical Technician, Supervisor, Team Lead etc...
	Skilled Mechanical	Service/Maintenance Technician, Mechanical Technician, Wind Turbine Technician, Statutory Inspector
	Semi-Skilled Mechanical	Fitter, Mechanic etc...
	Manual Mechanical	Manual mechanical operative, stores, helper etc...
Marine & Ports	Marine & Ports Senior/Management	Captain, Skipper, Mooring Master etc... OIM, DPO, SSL (Section Stability Leader), Harbour Master
	Skilled Marine & Ports	1st Officer, DPO, Marine Engineer, SSL, Pilots etc...
	Semi-Skilled Marine & Ports	Crane Operator, Drivers, Warehouse Operatives, Stores Operative, Deck Operator, Deck Crew
	Manual Marine & Ports	Mate, Deckhand, Able Seafarer, Quayside Operative, Stevedores, facilities crew etc...
Aviation	Aviation Senior/Management	Pilot etc...
	Skilled Aviation	Navigator, Senior Crew etc...
	Semi-Skilled Aviation	HLO etc...
	Manual Aviation	Groundcrew, Loading Crew etc...
Subsea	Subsea Senior/Management	Diving Supervisor, Survey Party Chief etc...
	Skilled-Subsea	Diver, ROV Pilot, Surveyor etc...

Job Family	Job Family Sub Group	Typical Role(s)
	Semi-Skilled-Subsea	Diver/Tech etc...Subsea Engineer
	Manual-Subsea	Deck Crew etc...

Appendix C: List of Sources and Contributors

- Acorn, 'Acorn CO₂ Transport and Storage', n.d,
- Air Liquide, 'Air Liquide to build a world-scale CO₂ capture unit to contribute to Rotterdam's industrial basin decarbonization', 2023
- AkerBP, 'Aker BP and OMV awarded licence for CO₂ storage', 2023
- Arthur Little, 'Nord Stream 2 Economic Impact on Europe, 2019
- Bellona Europa, 'EU CO₂ Infrastructure in Bloom: PCI/PMI Candidates Spread South and East, Become Multimodal, Cross-border, and Storage-Centred', n.d,
- Bitfrost, 'Bitfrost, - offshore CO₂ transport and storage project', n.d,
- Canadian Climate Institute, 'Managing a just transition in Denmark, 2022
- Carbon Capture & Sequestration Technologies, 'Sleipner Fact Sheet : Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage Project', 2016
- Carbon Capture Journal, 'BlueHyNow hydrogen and CCS project at Wilhelmshaven Energy Hub'. 2022
- CCS4CEE, 'Geothermal CCS Croatia', n.d,
- Croatian Hydrocarbon Agency, 'Geothermal CCS', n.d,
- CSLF, 'Northern Lights – Presentation and status update', 2022
- Enerdata, 'Development of the CO₂ Capture, Storage and Recovery (CCUS) sector in France: Prospective study of business and skills needs by 2050, 2024
- Enerdata, 'Sval and partners apply for a CO₂ storage licence off Norway, 2023
- Energy Press, 'REPowerEU: €75m for DESFA pipeline serving Prinos CCS', 2023
- Eni, 'Ravenna CCS project', n.d,
- Equinor, 'CCS on Sleipner – back where it came from', 2024
- Equinor, 'Smeaheai – bringing large scale CO₂ storage to European industry', 2024 (updated)
- Europa, 'Technical information on Projects of Common Interest and Projects of Mutual Interest', 2024
- European Commission, 'The emerging EU CO₂ transport and storage market', 2023
- European Commission, 'Karios@C : Building strong momentum for massive decarbonisation in the EU through a unique end-to-end CCS project', 2022
- European Commission, 'Shaping the future CO₂ transport network for Europe' 2024
- Fluxys, 'Ghent Carbon Hub', 2023
- Gasunie, 'Delta Rhine Corridor', 2024 (updated)
- Global CCS Institute, 'CCS in Europe Regional Overview', 2023
- Global CCS Institute, 'Denmark's Project Greensand Begins Groundbreaking Cross-border CO₂ Injection, 2023
- Global CCS Institute, 'Global Status of CCS 2023: Scaling Up Through 2030', 2023
- Hays, 'Jobs of the Future: Oil & Gas', 2015
- Holcim, KODECO net zero: CCS Knowledge sharing workshop by the innovation fund',

- Horisont Energi, 'Polaris: A complete and sustainable value chain for carbon capture - ,transport and storage', n.d,
- IDRIC, 'South Wales Industrial Cluster', 2022
- INSEE, 'Payroll employment at end of quarter - Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products; mining and quarrying; energy, water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation activities (A17-C2DE) - France excluding Mayotte', 2024
- ITA, 'Belgium – Country Commercial Guide', 2024
- IOGP, 'CCS projects in Europe', 2019
- IOGP, 'Map of CO₂ Storage Projects in Europe', 2023
- IOGP, 'Petrokemija Kutina', n.d,
- MOL Group, 'CO₂ EOR Project Croatia', 2017
- Neptune Energy, 'L10 CCS project : The CO₂ storage solution to help you achieve your climate goals', 2022
- Neptune Energy, 'Neptune Energy and Horisont Energi to cooperate on Errai CCS project, Norway', 2022
- NLOG, 'Oil and gas', n.d,
- Norne Carbon Storage Hub, 'About Project Norne', n.d,
- Norsk Petroleum, 'Employment in the Petroleum Industry', 2024 (updated)
- Offshore Energy, 'Dutch energy companies sign contract for Porthos CO₂ project', 2021
- OGE, 'H2morrow – act today to be greenhouse gas neutral by 2050', 2024 (updated)
- Opito, 'Energy Skills Intelligence Hub' 2024 (updated)
- Pycasso, 'A territorial project servinf the decarbonization od industry in the Pyrenean foothills, n.d,
- The Solent Cluster, 'Helping Transform Our Region: Socioeconomic Report', 2023
- The Solent Cluster, 'Why The Solent Custer', 2024 (updated)
- SSRN, 'Norwegian Hydrogen Value Chain Demonstration Based on Decarbonized Natural Gas', 2021
- Statista, 'Total number of employees in the crude petroleum and natural gas extraction sector in Italy from 2009 to 2020', 2024
- The CCUS Hub, 'Antwerp@C', n.d,
- The CCUS Hub, 'Aramis', n.d,
- Teesworks, 'Net Zero Teesside', n.d,
- Trudvang, 'Trudvang – A Sustainable future by reducing climate emissions through ccs', n.d,
- University of Edinburgh, 'Barents Blue: Project Details', 2021
- Viking CCS, 'The Project', 2024 (updated), n.d,
- Viking CCS, 'Viking CCS: Transforming the Humber into a net zero Superplace', 2023
- Viking CCS, 'Viking CCS Pipeline', 2023
- Wintershall Dea, 'Establishing a Complete CCS Infrastructure', n.d,
- Wintershall Dea, 'Wintershall Dea awarded second storage licence for CO₂ in Norway', 2023